

Developing measures of mental healthcare accessibility: a case study of Liverpool

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Summary

The accessibility of mental healthcare (MHC) is a complex notion reflecting wider health (in)equalities. However, existing research typically either ignores MHC or examines determinants of MHC accessibility (MHCA) in isolation. This paper develops a comprehensive analytical framework to conceptualise the patient's journey in accessing MHC as a process of distinct yet interrelated dimensions and operationalises it through developing a composite MHCA metric. It combines spatial and non-spatial aspects using floating catchment area modelling, factor analysis, and multi-criteria decision analysis, illustrating the approach using Liverpool (UK) as a case study. This demonstrates spatial and non-spatial barriers compounding, creating persistent disadvantage patterns.

KEYWORDS: mental health disorders, mental healthcare accessibility, accessibility measures, mental health inequalities and inequities

1. Introduction

In the UK, it is estimated that 1 in 6 adults experience common mental health problems each week (Baker and Kirk-Wade, 2024). Ensuring timely access to MHC is therefore key to maintaining or improving public health (Gulliford *et al.*, 2002). Despite this need, the UK faces a growing treatment gap for people with mental health disorders (MHDs). Substantial geographical variation in service provision persists. For example, waiting times for talking therapies can vary from 4 days as long as 79 days across different parts of England (Baker and Kirk-Wade, 2024). In response, improving equitable access to MHC through the National Health Service (NHS) has become a policy priority, prompting investments of £16 billion on mental health services in 2022/23, equivalent to 14% of local NHS funding allocations (Department of Health, 2011; Garratt and Laing, 2022; Murdoch and Kendall, 2016; NHS, 2014; NHS England, 2019).

Achieving such policy ambitions, however, requires an understanding of how access is experienced unevenly across places and population groups. In the general health context, accessibility is commonly conceptualised as the potential or opportunity to obtain care, meaning that it is often defined as the ease with which appropriate services can be reached and used in proportion to need (Levesque, Harris and Russell, 2013). Research has traditionally emphasised spatial and geographical dimensions of healthcare access (HCA), such as the location and reachability of services (Gulliford *et al.*, 2002; Salkever, 1976; Cheng *et al.*, 2020; Peters *et al.*, 2008), as well as some work addressing non-spatial dimensions, such as social, cultural and financial status (Khan, 1992; Subal, Paal and Krisp, 2021; Tadmon and Bearman, 2023; Salkever, 1976). Furthermore, work in this field is typically separated into patient-level 'help-seeking' behaviour and organisation-level health services research, further dividing elements affecting HCA. However, these dimensions are often analysed in isolation, even though accessing healthcare is in reality a multidimensional process that requires integrated measures capable of capturing how spatial and non-spatial barriers interact across locations. This fragmentation

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limits the ability of existing approaches to identify compounded disadvantage and to inform targeted, equity-oriented healthcare planning.

MHC in particular represents a domain in which accessibility constraints are particularly relevant. Pathways to MHC are shaped by the spatial distribution of services and also by less tangible factors such as social stigma, cultural acceptability, financial constraints and the capacity to navigate healthcare systems. These factors often intersect and reinforce one another, giving rise to compounded accessibility barriers for people with mental health needs and further highlighting the need for integrated, multidimensional approaches to understanding and measuring access to MHC.

This work addresses these gaps by contributing to the conceptualisation and measurement of MHCA. We propose an analytical framework that considers accessibility to MHC as a holistic process involving several dimensions mostly segregated in existing literature. Accessibility is then operationalised via a composite metric that combines spatial and non-spatial measures of accessibility. The framework is illustrated through a case study of Liverpool (UK), focusing on NHS publicly provided general mental health services for common mental health disorders (CMHDs), including depression, generalised anxiety disorder, social anxiety, panic disorder, obsessive-compulsive disorder, post-traumatic stress disorder and phobias (McManus *et al.*, 2016; National Collaborating Centre for Mental Health *et al.*, 2011). Liverpool provides a compelling empirical setting due to its disproportionate burden of CMHDs, with a higher rate of depression than both the North-West and England as a whole (see **Table 1**) and clear spatial patterns of mental health need (see **Figure 1**).

Table 1: GP patients aged 18+ diagnosed with depression

Area	Average (%)
Liverpool (in Merseyside)	17.99
North-West	16.44
England	13.25

Source: adapted from House of Commons data dashboard, "Constituency data: health conditions" (Harker, Stiebahl and Baker, 2025)

Figure 1 Map of mental health need using Small Area Mental Health Index (SAMHI) from Daras and Barr (2021). Higher deciles correspond to higher mental health need and worse mental health.

Specifically, this study aims to address the following research questions:

RQ1: How can we comprehensively conceptualise the process of accessing mental healthcare?

RQ2: How can we construct a holistic and comprehensive measure of mental healthcare accessibility in a quantitative way?

RQ3: What are the spatial patterns of mental healthcare accessibility revealed by applying these measures to Liverpool, UK?

2. Methods

2.1 Conceptual framework

The study develops a process-based framework for understanding MHCA. This framework is developed using existing literature on general healthcare access and service utilisation. The framework conceptualises access to MHC as a process, formed by a sequence of stages that individuals must be able to navigate through in order to receive care (summarised in **Figure 2**). The framework explicitly incorporates both spatial and non-spatial factors and positions these in terms of how they relate to patients and treatment services, illustrating these crossovers and thus demonstrating the richness of examining these together (see **Figure 3**). These factors also all have spatial expressions and variation across sociodemographic groups, adding a further layer to motivate this holistic approach. The framework thus serves as the theoretical grounding to inform the development of measures of MHCA, thus overcoming the conceptual fragmentation commonly found in the literature.

Figure 2 Diagram of proposed process for gaining access to mental health treatment

2.2 Measuring mental healthcare accessibility

Spatial accessibility is measured using the enhanced two-step floating catchment area method (E2SFCA) (Luo and Qi, 2009), implemented following Nagy (n.d.), to account for the distribution of MHC services, population demand and distance decay effects. Non-spatial accessibility is captured using socio-demographic and contextual indicators, which are synthesised through principal component analysis (PCA) and both exploratory (EFA) and confirmatory (CFA) factor analysis, following approaches in healthcare accessibility research Szczęsna (2022), Hartmann, Krois and Rudolph (2023), Murphy (2021), and Whalley (n.d.). The resulting spatial and non-spatial accessibility scores are integrated into a composite MHCA metric using ELECTRE-III (Elimination and(et) Choice Translating Reality), a multi-criteria decision analysis (MCDA) method that allows for non-compensatory trade-offs between dimensions. Final scores are scaled and converted into percentile rankings for mapping and interpretation. The framework is applied to Liverpool (UK), focusing on publicly provided specialist MHC services delivered by the local NHS mental health trust, Mersey Care.

3. Results and discussion

This study produces a composite measure of MHCA that integrates two complementary dimensions, spatial and non-spatial accessibility. These components capture accessibility as a multidimensional process, combining previously divided notions of different phases in access, features of patients and services, and spatial and non-spatial factors impacting accessibility. When applied to the context of Liverpool, these measures reveal consistent inequalities in MHCA (see **Figure 4**). The areas with the lowest levels of composite MHCA are observed in the south (postcode L24) and northwest (L20 and surrounding areas) of the city. The composite measures also identify some parts of the east (L27) and west (L8) as further areas experiencing poor mental healthcare accessibility, which are areas which not only have experienced historic deprivation but also experience higher levels of mental health need (see **Figure 1**). These patterns are less evident when considering either spatial or non-spatial dimensions in isolation, which demonstrates that reliance on a single dimension of accessibility risks underestimating compounded disadvantages.

Figure 4 i) Bivariate mapping of aggregated component scores ii) composite accessibility score, where lower values indicate better accessibility

In addition to identifying areas of low accessibility, the results illustrate the analytical value of integrating spatial and non-spatial dimensions within a single metric. Areas characterised by relatively adequate spatial accessibility may have low overall accessibility once non-spatial barriers are accounted for. This highlights the importance of a multidimensional approach to measuring access to mental healthcare.

4. Conclusion

In applying the measure of MHCA to Liverpool, spatial patterns are identified which correspond with patterns of mental health need. This indicates that further efforts need to be made to both understand the drivers of this disadvantage, and to establish targeted interventions to improve access to mental health treatment.

Our findings also have broader policy relevance. Improving access to MHC has the potential to increase treatment uptake for mental health disorders, contributing to improved mental health and wellbeing at the population level. In this sense, the study aligns with the United Nations' Sustainable Development Goal 3, which emphasises the promotion of health and wellbeing.

It is important to also recognise the limitations of this work. First, the transport modes included in the spatial accessibility score do not apply to everyone and exclude those who face challenges in taking part in active transport such as walking or cycling. Second, the lack of openly available service utilisation data limits the ability to validate the accessibility measures against observed service use. Finally, whilst primarily interested in the spatial expressions of patterns of MHC accessibility, the non-spatial accessibility measure does not pertain to any inherent features of areas, but instead an analysis of the communities that live there. Nonetheless, these results still provide an opportunity to recognise the areas in which specific communities may benefit from targeted interventions.

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Biographies

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Carmen is a Lecturer in Geographic Data Science at the University of Liverpool. Her research focuses on the study spatiotemporal patterns of human mobility and social behaviours across population groups and locations, with techniques such as statistical modelling and network analysis.